

Appendix A. Student Evaluation Questionnaire

The questionnaire used in this study was developed and administered by the Quality Assurance Unit (QAU) of the university. It contains both quantitative (closed-ended) and qualitative (open-ended) items. The feedback was collected anonymously at the end of the academic semester.

Section A – Closed-ended questions (Likert scale)

1. The instructor was well-prepared for the teaching sessions.
2. The course content was clearly presented and well-structured.
3. The instructor encouraged student participation.
4. The use of digital resources supported learning effectively.
5. The pace and workload of the course were appropriate.
6. Overall, I am satisfied with the quality of the teaching provided.

Section B – Open-ended questions

7. What aspects of the instructor's teaching did you find most effective?
8. What improvements would you suggest regarding the course or instructor?

Note: The exact phrasing and structure of the questionnaire follow institutional templates aligned with the National Higher Education Assessment Authority guidelines.